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*¹Author1, A. B, ²Author2 C. D and ^{1,3}Author3 E. F.

¹Author1 affiliation with the prescribed formatting

²Author2 affiliation with the prescribed formatting

³Author3 affiliation with the prescribed formatting

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ABSTRACT

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***1** **CORRESPONDING AUTHOR** | Author1 A. B. | ✉author1@email.com

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1 Introduction

Half-Heusler compounds (HHE) is a family of compounds possessing broad and enchanting qualities and applications. They have a cubic $C1b$ crystal structure in the space group $F4'3m$ which is a three inter-penetrating face-centered-cubic-lattices. In a normal HHE with the general formula XYZ , the X atom is a heavier transition element, Y is a lighter transition element or a rare-earth and Z is a late main-group element [1]. Also, there are three available atomic arrangements for the XYZ atoms often termed Type-1, Type-2 and Type-3. The atomic arrangements (respectively Wyckoff positions) are the following: Type-1 ($4b$ (1/2, 1/2, 1/2), $4c$ (1/4, 1/4, 1/4), $4a$ (0, 0, 0)); Type-2 ($4b$ (1/2, 1/2, 1/2), $4a$ (0, 0, 0), $4c$ (1/4, 1/4, 1/4)) and Type-3 ($4c$ (1/4, 1/4, 1/4), $4b$ (1/2, 1/2, 1/2), $4a$ (0, 0, 0)). Also, in the $C1b$ structure, Y atoms constitute a rock-salt (NaCl)-like sublattice with the Z atoms while the X atoms on the other hand form a zinc-blende-like lattice with the Z atoms.

The properties of the HHE phases significantly differ methodically along with the valence electron content (VEC), which is the periodic table prescribed valences. These HHEs are characterized by large magnetic moments and high Curie temperatures [2], [3] relative to the binary and associated phases [4]. In some HHEs, while the minority spin component displays an energy gap character at the Fermi level, the majority spin component exhibits metallic qualities as evidenced in the electronic structure. This phenomenon is called half-metallic ferromagnetic (HMF) character which culminates into 100% spin-polarized materials with high potential for technological applications in spintronics [5,7]. The inclusion of the spin accompaniment to the traditional semiconductor electronics has a lot of leverages such as, reduced electric power utilization, faster data processing speed, expanded integration densities and non-volatility [8].

FeCrAs alloy has been studied in two major phases: hexagonal and the HHE phase. Nylund *et al.* [9] synthesized hexagonal FeCrAs in the space group $P6'm2$ (No. 187). He *et al.* [10] investigated the crystal structure, elastic constants, thermodynamic and electronic properties of the novel hexagonal FeCrAs under high pressure using density functional theory. The electronic structure calculations of the hexagonal FeCrAs were performed with full-potential linearized augmented plane-wave (FPLAPW) method and the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) by Akrap *et al.* [11] where they assumed a paramagnetic ground state and non-interacting spins in these materials. Djelti *et al.* [12], Hao *et al.* [13] and Feng *et al.* [14] studied FeCrAs compounds in the half-Heusler structure with ferromagnetic ground state while Fujii *et al.* [15] obtained ferrimagnetic ground state for the half-Heusler FeCrAs (HHFCA) using FPLAPW method. The different ground states obtained using various approaches

suggest that FeCrAs has different polymorphs. The results also suggest that the hexagonal phase is stabilized at high pressure while HHE phase is stabilized at ambient and reduced pressure.

In the present study, using the DFT approach, we examine the relative stability of hexagonal and HHE phases of FeCrAs alloy. Also, we determine originally the elastic constants and mechanical properties of FeCrAs in the HHE.

2 Computational Methodology/Materials & Methods

An ab-initio DFT spin polarized calculations [16,17] have been performed using the corrected exchange correlation functional of Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBEsol) [18] which is a generalized gradient approximation (GGA). This functional have been shown to produce more accurately the equilibrium bulk and surface properties of close-packed solids. For these computations, plane-wave basis sets, as enabled in the Quantum-Espresso program package [19] was adopted. Electronic kinetic energy cutoff of 80 Ry with energy convergence benchmark of 10⁻⁸ Ry was utilized. Scalar relativistic norm-conserving pseudopotentials [20] were used to estimate the repulsion between ions and valence electrons. For the elements making up the HHE, the following are the valence electronic configurations: Fe: $4s, 4d, 3d$; Cr: $4s, 4p, 3d$, and As: $4s, 4d$. Sampling of k -points in the Brillouin zone was done with 12 x 12 x 12 grid with Monkhorst-Pack scheme [21] in the primitive unit cell of half-Heusler FeCrAs alloy presented in Figure 1. The Brillouin zone integration was carried out using the Marzari-Vanderbilt cold smearing scheme with a parameter of 0.01 Ry and total energy convergence ~ 1 mRy/atom. The ionic geometry relaxation was relaxed to ~ 0.1 mRy for total energy and 1 mRy/au for the forces on the atoms. The equilibrium lattice constant of HHFCA was obtained from the total energy-lattice constants relation and fitting the calculated values to the Murnaghan equation of state [22]. The spin polarization P is calculated using Eqn. (1) [23].

$$\sigma_i = \sum^6 c_{ij} \epsilon_{ij} \quad (1)$$

where $DEF\uparrow$ and $DEF\downarrow$ are the density of states appearing at the Fermi level for spin-up and spin-down respectively. The electronic structure calculations of the hexagonal FeCrAs were performed with full-potential linearized augmented plane-wave (FPLAPW) method and the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) by Akrap *et al.* [11] where they assumed a paramagnetic ground state and non-interacting spins in these materials. Djelti *et al.* [12], Hao *et al.* [13] and Feng *et al.* [14] studied FeCrAs compounds in the half-Heusler structure with ferromagnetic ground state while Fujii *et al.* [15] obtained ferrimagnetic ground state for the half-Heusler FeCrAs (HHFCA) using FPLAPW method.

3 Results and Discussions

3.1 Structural and elastic properties

We investigated the total energy of the two main structural phases of the FeCrAs alloy reported in the literature [10,12,14,15], namely the hexagonal and half-Heusler phases. First, we performed total energy calculations for the Type-1, Type-2 and Type-3 phases of a half-Heusler structures. Our result shows that the Type-3 phase is the most stable phase as presented in Figure 2. We compared the structural stability of the hexagonal (Figure 1(a)) and the half-Heusler structure (Figure 1(b)). The magnetic ground state of the hexagonal polymorph is ferrimagnetic while that for the half-Heusler is ferromagnetic. Our result shows that the hexagonal polymorph is the high-pressure phase. However, at the equilibrium lattice constant of the half-Heusler phase, both the hexagonal and half-Heusler phase have the same volume and total energy and so appears to be in equilibrium as presented in Figure 3. The equilibrium lattice constant of 5.59 Å obtained in our calculation is in consonance with previous results presented in Table 1.

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Table 1: The lattice constant and system parameters

Lattice (Å)	Pressure (Gpa)	β(Gpa)			Shear Modulus α(Gpa)
		Training	Testing	Total	
1.32	15.76	56.78	7890	5600	8.900
1.45	56.77	88.89	4200	7866	9.003
1.32	15.76	56.78	7890	5600	8.900
1.45	56.77	88.89	4200	7866	9.003

Three elastic constants comprising C11, C12 and C44 are vital to get the stability criteria of a cubic crystal. For a crystal subjected to strain by exerting stress presented as a stress tensor σ_i , for marginal magnitude of strain tensor ϵ_j , the two tensors are related by [5]

$$\sigma_i = \sum^6 C_{ij} \epsilon_{ij} \quad (2)$$

The electronic properties of the HHFCA were studied using spin-polarized DFT calculations. The density of states from the atomic orbitals (PDOS) of the Fe, Cr and As are presented in Figure 4(a), (b) & (c). The maximum of the valence band in the spin down component consists mainly of the Fe-3d orbitals while the maximum of the occupied states in the spin up component is basically that of the Cr-3d orbitals. Also, the bottom of the conduction band (which is unoccupied) in the spin down channel consists largely of the Cr-3d states. Figure 4 (d) is the total density of states (DOS) which shows that the spin up DOS is metallic while the spin down DOS displays electronic energy gap. It can be deduced from Figures 4(a-c) that the Fe-3d and Cr-3d orbitals is responsible for the electronic energy band gap in the spin down component. Figure 5 is the electronic band structure of the HHFCA. The spin up is metallic (Figure 5(a)) while the spin down electronic structure (Figure 5(b)) exhibits an indirect band gap with the top of the valence band at the symmetry point Γ and the bottom of the valence band located at the symmetry points X in the Brillouin zone. The top of the valence band in the

spin down band structure is triply degenerate while the bottom of the conduction band in the spin down component is doubly degenerate.

3.2 Conclusion

The structural, elastic, mechanical, electronic and magnetic properties of the HHFCA have been studied using the spin-polarized DFT calculations. Our result showed that hexagonal phase is the stable phase at high pressure while the HHE phase is the more stable at ambient pressure. Our result show that Type-3 is the HHE structural ground state with ferromagnetic configuration. The HHFCA is mechanically stable, brittle and anisotropic. Electronic properties showed that HHFCA exhibits half-metallic ferromagnetism with an indirect band gap of 1.16 eV in the minority spin channel and 100% spin polarization around the Fermi level. The result of the magnetic properties showed that the total magnetic moment contained in one formula unit is 1.00 μ_B in consonance with the Slater-Pauling prediction. The bulk of the magnetic moment resides on the Cr atoms. High Curie temperature was obtained for HHFCA which suggests that the compound is promising for spintronic applications. High Curie temperature was obtained for HHFCA which suggests that the compound is promising for spintronic applications.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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